

the environment. Therefore, we need to characterize parental lines, especially restorers, using biotechnological tools.

DNA was extracted from commonly used parental stocks (CMS lines IR58025A and IR62829A; their isonuclear maintainer (B) lines IR58025B and IR62829B; and elite restorer (R) lines IR40750, IR9761, IR34686, and IR10198. These extracted DNA samples were amplified by polymerase chain reaction using 20 arbitrary oligo-nucleotide primers. The amplified products were analyzed on agarose gel and scored for the presence or absence of bands. With selected primers (OPA-7, OPA-12, OPA-20, OPB-19, OPU-17, and OPW-4), sufficient polymorphism could be detected to allow identification of individual stocks. The isonuclear maintainer and the CMS lines were, however, indistinguishable. The randomly amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD) analysis is a potentially simple, rapid, and reliable DNA finger-printing method for identifying parental stocks and determining the parentage of rice hybrids. As this molecular technique verifies the degree of dissimilarity between the parental lines, the RAPD analysis may also help in identifying new potential combinations based on genetic divergence. ■

Exploiting the in vitro ovary culture technique to breed rice hybrids

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The thermosensitive genic male sterility (TGMS) system has a high potential to develop two-line hybrids, which are more economical for seed production. The ovary culture technique can also help to improve or develop new lines for several economic traits. We therefore cultured unpollinated ovaries from plants of five crosses involving TGMS UPRI 95-140 (P1), the good

ideotype UPRI 95-117 (P2), and maintainers UPRI 95-139 (P3) and UPRI 95-130 (P4). Quality rices—Basmati 385 (P5), Haryana Basmati 1 (P6), and UPRI 95-145 (P7)—were also cultured. The cultured ovary from hybrid plants P1/P2 pretreated at 8 °C for 14 d on an N6 medium supplemented with 500 mg lactoprotein hydrolysate (LH) L⁻¹, 4 mg 2,4-D L⁻¹, 2 mg NAA L⁻¹, and 1 mg BA L⁻¹ produced 0.5% calli. Regeneration of these calli on an MS medium containing 500 mg casein acid hydrolysate L⁻¹, 0.5 mg NAA L⁻¹, and 1.5 mg BA L⁻¹ produced four clumps of completely green plantlets and one partially green plantlet. One of these green plantlets showed the TGMS trait. It was completely spikelet sterile during the panicle heading period between 15 Jun and 5 Sep, but was partially fertile and set seed after 18 Sep. Seed set was 0.5, 1.7, 4.8, 12.3, and 6.4% at heading on 18 Sep, 1 Oct, 12 Oct, 26 Oct, and 1 Nov 1995, respectively. The ovary culture-derived line was dwarf, with an intermediate plant type, and flag leaf and

panicle length similar to those of the female parent. But this line produced more spikelets.

The unpollinated ovaries of F₁ plants derived from maintainer/quality rices cultured on an N6 medium supplemented with 0.5 mg 2,4-D L⁻¹, 4 mg NAA L⁻¹, and 1.0 mg BA L⁻¹ produced calli. Callus induction was 3.33, 2.67, 1.33, and 2.00% for P5/P3, P3/P5, P6/P4, and P7/P4, respectively. But plantlets were regenerated only from P5/P3 (46.7%) and P3/P5 (50.0%) on an N6 regeneration medium supplemented with 500 mg LH L⁻¹, 0.5 mg NAA L⁻¹, and 2 mg kinetin L⁻¹. The performance of seven H1 clones of the former cross showed four clones with long, bold grain and a nontranslucent endosperm, whereas clones 6 and 7 had long, slender grains and a translucent endosperm free of an opaque area and were comparable in quality with Basmati 385. Exploitation of these lines to improve quality and yield potential in a hybrid rice breeding program is in progress. ■

Pest resistance — diseases

A variety with durable resistance to rice blast

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San-Huang-Zhan No. 2 (SHZ), a rice variety developed by the Guangdong Academy of Agricultural Sciences, was cultivated on 1,533 ha in 1986. It then spread from 8,000 ha in 1987 to 10,977 ha in 1995 and showed excellent resistance to blast in an environment favorable to blast in Guangdong, China. Therefore, we assumed that SHZ is a variety with durable resistance to blast.

Looking at the resistance performance of SHZ, we found that its resistance spectrum (RS) was more than 95% from 1985 to 1995 (Table 1). In 1995, the RS of SHZ was 99.5% under artificial inoculation with 220 isolates in Guangdong and 95.2% with 124

isolates of *Pyricularia grisea* from eight rice-growing zones in China. Furthermore, we screened a stable isolate (GD-V1) that is compatible to SHZ to investigate the reaction of SHZ compared with the reaction of the resistant check IR36 and the susceptible check B40. Entries were inoculated at the 5-leaf stage. Lesion density (LD) and lesion size (LS) were scored by the method of Roumen and diseased leaf area (DLA) was measured by the method of Notteghem. To make a better comparison, we converted the observed data (OD) of LD, LS, and DLA into relative value (RV) on the basis of B40, and computed the mean of LD, LS, and DLA. At the same time, resistance of the varieties was assessed in fields in eight rice-growing zones in China by the Standard of the National Blast Co-research Group. Results (Table 2) indicated that the resistance of SHZ and IR36 is different because SHZ